

Study of Risk Factors for Severe Acute Malnutrition with Respect to Clinical and Demographic Profile

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 07-09-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM) remains a significant public health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where it is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality among children under five years of age. Understanding the clinical and demographic factors contributing to SAM is crucial for effective prevention and intervention strategies.

Aim and Objective: This study aimed to identify key clinical and demographic risk factors associated with Severe Acute Malnutrition in children aged 6 to 59 months.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital and its affiliated community health centers CAIMS, Karimnagar. A total of 110 children diagnosed with SAM, based on WHO criteria, were enrolled. Data collection involved a structured questionnaire addressing demographic profiles, clinical histories, and household characteristics. Statistical analyses included bivariate analysis and multivariate logistic regression to determine independent risk factors for SAM.

Results: The study found that low parental education, large family size, and low socioeconomic status were significant demographic risk factors for SAM. Clinically, a history of recurrent infections, poor immunization coverage, and inadequate breastfeeding practices were strongly associated with SAM. Multivariate analysis indicated that recurrent infections and low socioeconomic status were the most significant predictors of SAM.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that both clinical and demographic factors play a crucial role in the development of SAM. Public health interventions should focus on improving maternal education, enhancing healthcare access, and promoting optimal feeding practices to reduce the incidence of SAM and improve child health outcomes.

Keywords: Severe Acute Malnutrition, Risk Factors, Clinical Profile, Demographic Profile, Child Health.

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Introduction

Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM) remains a critical public health concern, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where it significantly contributes to child morbidity and mortality. The condition is characterized by extreme wasting, with a weight-for-height measurement significantly below the median, or by the presence of nutritional edema. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), SAM affects millions of children under five years of age, making it a priority for global health initiatives.

The multifactorial nature of SAM suggests that a combination of clinical and demographic factors plays a pivotal role in its development and severity. These factors include but are not limited to, socioeconomic status, maternal education, household food security, access to healthcare services, and underlying medical conditions such as infections and chronic illnesses. Understanding

these risk factors is essential for the development of effective interventions aimed at preventing and managing SAM, ultimately reducing its prevalence and associated mortality.

Despite numerous studies highlighting the prevalence and consequences of SAM, there is still a need for comprehensive research that delineates the specific risk factors associated with its development. This study aims to bridge this gap by examining the clinical and demographic profiles of children diagnosed with SAM. By identifying the key risk factors, this research seeks to provide valuable insights that can inform public health strategies, healthcare policies, and community-based interventions targeted at reducing the burden of SAM.

The importance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on malnutrition, particularly in regions where SAM is

most prevalent. By focusing on the clinical and demographic aspects, this research not only seeks to identify vulnerable populations but also to understand the interplay between various risk factors that exacerbate the condition. This, in turn, could lead to more targeted and effective interventions that address the root causes of SAM, thereby improving the health outcomes of affected children and contributing to broader efforts to achieve global health equity.

Materials and Method

This was a cross-sectional, observational analysis aimed at identifying and evaluating the risk factors associated with Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM) in children under the age of five. The study was carried out in a tertiary care hospital and affiliated community health center of CAIMS Karimnagar. The chosen sites are representative of the region's population and serve a diverse demographic, making them ideal for studying the varied risk factors associated with SAM.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Children aged 6 months to 59 months who were diagnosed with SAM according to the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria
2. presence of nutritional edema
3. Those who were ready to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria

1. Children presenting with other forms of malnutrition.
2. Children with less than 6 months and more than 5 years.

Sample Size :

According to the study conducted by “: Ulahannan SK, Wilson A, Chhetri D, et al. Alarming level of severe acute malnutrition in Indian districts. *BMJ Global Health* 2022;7:e007798. doi:10.1136/bmjgh-2021-007798”[1] prevalence of severe acute malnutrition was 7.6%, so considering this prevalence at 95% confidence and 5% level of significance sample size calculated as given below by Cochran's

formula was 101, and considering 10% loss of data final sample size was 110.

Method

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which was administered by trained healthcare professionals. The questionnaire was divided into three sections: demographic profile, clinical profile, and household characteristics. The following variables were included:

1. Demographic Profile:

- Age and gender of the child
- Parental age and education level
- Family size and socioeconomic status
- Residence (urban or rural)

2. Clinical Profile:

- Anthropometric measurements (weight, height/length, mid-upper arm circumference)
- Presence of nutritional edema
- History of infections or chronic illnesses (e.g., diarrhea, respiratory infections, HIV)
- Immunization status
- Feeding practices (breastfeeding and complementary feeding practices)

Statistical Analysis

Collected data were entered in the Microsoft Excel for further statistical analysis, categorical data were expressed in terms of frequency and percentages, while quantitative data were expressed in terms of mean and standard deviation. Descriptive statistics has performed. Statistical analysis was done with the help of statistical software SPSS version 25

Observation and Results

This study conducted for duration of one and half year to examined the clinical and demographic profiles of children diagnosed with SAM. By identifying the key risk factors, and their observation were given below.

Table 1 : Distribution of Demographic profile of study sample

Parameters	Frequency	Percentages
Age		
6 - 12 Months	22	20
1 -2 Years	48	43.6
2 - 3 years	19	17.3
3 - 4 Years	13	11.8
4 - 5 Years	8	7.3
Gender		
Male	51	46.4
Female	59	53.6
Maternal Age		

< 20 Years	21	19.1
21 - 30 Years	51	46.4
31-40 Years	28	25.5
> 40 Years	10	9.1
Residence		
Urban	39	35.5
Rural	61	55.5
Maternal Education		
Illiterate	38	34.5
Primary	14	12.7
Highschool + Intermediate	41	37.3
Graduate	10	9.1
Post Graduate and higher	7	6.4
Family Type		
Joint	28	25.5
Nuclear	72	65.5
Socio Economic Status		
Lower Class	36	32.7
Upper Lower	42	38.2
Lower Middle	23	20.9
Middle	6	5.5
Upper Class	3	2.7

Table 2 : Distribution of immunization status, birth order and feeding practices

Parameters	Frequency	Percentages
Immunization Status		
Completed	32	29.1
Not Completed	71	64.5
Non-Immunized	7	6.4
Birth Order		
1	19	17.3
2	40	36.4
≥3	51	46.4
Feeding Practices		
Breastfeeding	56	50.9
Formula Feed	39	35.5
Animal Milk	15	13.6

Table 3 : Distribution of Clinical parameters among study population

Parameters	Frequency	Percentages
Infections(n=66)		
Acute gastroenteritis	31	47
Acute respiratory tract infections	14	21.2
UTI	8	12.1
Measles	7	10.6
Tuberculosis	3	4.5
Sepsis	3	4.5
Metabolic Disturbance(n=64)		
Hypoglycaemia	18	28.1
Hypokalaemia	11	17.2
Hyponatremia	7	10.9
Hypernatremia	4	6.3
Dehydration	24	37.5
Micronutrient Deficiency		
Rickets	9	8.2
Iron Deficiency Anaemia	63	57.3
Vitamin A	14	12.7
Vitamin B	24	21.8

Table 4 : Distribution of Clinical parameters among study population

Parameters	OR	p-value
Maternal Education		
Illiterate	5.23	<0.05
Primary	1.96	>0.05
Highschool + Intermediate	2.13	>0.05
Graduate	1.72	>0.05
Post Graduate and higher	Reference	
Socio Economic Status		
Lower Class	4.11	<0.05
Upper Lower	2.61	>0.05
Lower Middle	1.36	>0.05
Middle	1.03	>0.05
Upper Class	Reference	
Type of Family		
Joint	3.94	<0.05
Nuclear	Reference	
Immunization Status		
Completed	Reference	
Not Completed	2.69	>0.05
Non Immunized	6.72	<0.05
Immunization Status		
Breastfeeding	Reference	
Formula Feed	4.92	<0.05
Animal Milk	2.91	>0.05

Discussion

Nutrition is essential for individual growth and is central to health and well-being. Preschool children, in particular, are a nutritionally vulnerable group. The nutrition they receive during the first five years of life influences not only their growth and development during this critical period but also plays a role in determining their nutritional status in adolescence and adulthood. Severe acute malnutrition (SAM) is a preventable and treatable cause of childhood illness and death. The nutritional status of children aged 6 to 59 months is influenced by a wide range of factors, making it a complex and multifaceted issue.

Demographic Profile

In the present study majority of the patients were from age group of 1-2 years(43.6%) followed by 6 months to 1 years(20%). [1] Study conducted by Najar BA et al observed that, maximum number of children (approximately 60.38%) were within 6-24 months of age. A similar study by Kumar et al who had reported 59.6% of children in the age group of 6-12 months. Similar study by Choudhary reported most of the cases (96% and 71% respectively) were less than two years. [2,3] During the first two years of life, rapid growth and development take place, increasing the need for energy and the building blocks of tissues. This heightened demand often results in deficiencies in energy, protein, and micronutrients, which can lead to malnutrition. Additionally, growth and nutritional needs are at their peak during this early stage of life.

In the present study, we have observed majority of the patients were female compared to males, A higher number of female patients was also found by Sharma et al (60%% versus 40%). [4] Shah et al and Rao et al also reported that the extent of malnutrition was significantly higher in girls (80%) respectively. [5,6] All these 3 studies were community-based studies. Syed et al, Choudhary et al and Goyal described higher incidence of malnutrition in males (54.5%, 74.6%, 53.7% and 84.3% respectively in their hospital-based studies. [3,6,7] They postulated that due to ritual and social norms, parents give more importance and seek medical advice more often for the male child. However, our study, despite being a hospital-based one, showed a higher number of female patients.

In our study, majority of the patients were from rural area, and mother education was high school and intermediate followed by illiterate and almost more than 70% of the patients were belonged to the lower and upper lower class and from nuclear family. Najar BA et al observed that observed that, maternal illiteracy rates were 64.28%, 18.75% of mothers studied up to primary school, 10.71% studied up to secondary and only 6.25% studied up to higher secondary and none up to college or degree. Higher illiteracy rates were described by Choudhary (89.3% mothers) and Goyal (60.6% mothers).[3,6] Other studies by Rajkumari Rupabati Devi et al, severe acute malnutrition was more common among the rural children than the urban and most of them significantly belonged to the lower socio-economic strata. These findings

were in accordance with a community-based control study done by David SM et al. [8] Tariq et al and Goyal et al reported 96% and 83.6% patients belonging to lower socio-economic strata. [6,7] This indicates that poor purchasing power, unavailability of food, improper distributions make the children vulnerable to malnutrition in a deprived community.

Clinical Parameters and Risk Factors

In the present study 64.5% of the patients were not with complete immunization, and nearly 50% of the children were on formula feed and animal feed and only 50.9% of the of the children were on breast feeding. In the present study we have observed that, 37.5% of the patients were dehydration followed by hypoglycaemia, hypokalaemia and hyponatremia. In our study almost 57.3% of the patients were observed with Iron Deficiency Anaemia, followed by vitamin B deficiency, vitamin A deficiency and rickets. Prevalence of SAM was 52% in the family having 3 or more children in the study by Choudhary et al. Sharma et al also reported the prevalence of malnutrition to be significantly higher in families having more than 3 children due to lower per capita income and poor childcare practices. [3,4] The percentages of exclusive breast feeding, mixed feeding and predominantly bottle feeding were 42.5%, 44% and 24% respectively study by Basvarajan et al comparable to our study. [13] Over diluted formula milk and cow's milk (56.67%) was the most common top milk supplementation in our study and a high incidence of bottle feeding have been reported by Basavarajan et al (45.5%), Choudhary et al (17.3%) comparable to our studies. [3,9] As per WHO and UNICEF recommendations, the infant should be exclusively breastfed for 1st six months of life to achieve optimal growth and development. Thereafter to meet their evolving nutritional requirement, infants should receive nutritionally adequate and safe complementary foods while breastfeeding continued up to 2 years of age. [10, 11]

Acute gastroenteritis 82.14% was the most common associated infection followed by acute respiratory tract infections 66.07% in our study comparable to similar studies. [7,12] The most common metabolic disturbances were hypoglycaemia 14.28% and hypokalemia 8.9% comparable to studies by Sharma et al and Syed et al. [8,11]

In the present study, we have observed that, children of uneducated women were more affected by SAM, also families with lower socio economic class were more affected compared to others economic groups. Study observed among joint families children observed with SAM and found to be one of the risk factor for SAM. Also children

with no immunization status and who were on the formula feed observed as risk factors for SAM. Tariq et al and Goyal et al reported 96% and 83.6% patients belonging to lower socio-economic strata. [6,7] This indicates that poor purchasing power, unavailability of food, improper distributions make the children vulnerable to malnutrition in a deprived community. Prevalence of SAM was 52% in the family having 3 or more children in the study by Choudhary et al. Sharma et al also reported the prevalence of malnutrition to be significantly higher in families having more than 3 children due to lower per capita income and poor childcare practices.

In a study done in Ethiopia it was observed that fully vaccinated children had a higher chance of getting recovered from severe acute malnutrition compared to partially or not vaccinated children. [13]

Conclusion

From above observation and after discussion with other studies we can conclude that, The problem of SAM is multidimensional and multifactorial. Lower maternal education, Joint family, low socioeconomic status of family, lack of exclusive breastfeeding, high birth order contribute to SAM. SAM is prevalent in children of 6-24 months of age. Dietary risk factors such as duration of exclusive breastfeeding, bottle feeding, and delayed introduction of complementary feeding were significantly associated with poor outcomes. Maternal Education, lower socio economic status, joint family, and status of immunization were found to be the risk factors for SAM. Screening should be routinely performed in all healthcare centers in the community for early detection of SAM children. Immunization and universal health coverage to all will help to reduce malnutrition and mortality among SAM children.

Acknowledgment: None.

Funding: None.

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